

Synthesis and Characterisation of Periodate and Periodato Compound of Gallium

L. C. W. BAKER

The Department of Chemistry, Georgetown University, Washington D. C., U. S. A.

and

H. G. MUKHERJEE* and S. B. SARKAR

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 23 April 1982, accepted 28 January 1983

Preparations of hitherto unknown gallium periodate and lithium salt of gallium periodate have been described. Their characterization with the help of elemental analysis, thermal, magnetic, potentiometric, chemical, electrophoretic, ir and diffused reflectance spectral and powder X-ray studies has been reported.

RECENT work¹ on periodato cobalt(III) complex reveals that the structure of polymeric periodato complex is similar to that of heteropolyacid. Preparation of indium periodate² and its study prompted us to prepare and study hitherto unknown gallium periodate and periodato compounds of gallium.

On the basis of analyses, thermal degradation, magnetic moment, ir spectra, diffuse reflectance spectra, oxidation number determination, potentiometric titration, electrophoresis and powder X-ray analysis, the gallium periodate can be assigned the formula $Ga_5(IO_6)_3 \cdot H_2O$ and the lithium gallium periodate $Li_7Ga(IO_6)_3 \cdot 4H_2O$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Thermal analysis was carried out on a manual derivatograph. Infrared spectrum was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, magnetic measurements on Guoy balance, diffused reflectance spectrum on a Cary 17D spectrophotometer. Powder X-ray photograph was recorded on a Guinear camera using Cu target.

Preparation of $Ga_5(IO_6)_3 \cdot H_2O$: Gallium sulphate (5 g) solution in water (25 ml) was added to a solution of $NaIO_4$ (2 g) in water (25 ml). pH of the

solution was kept at ~ 3 . The mixture was stirred for 3 hr with a magnetic stirrer. A white precipitate was obtained which was filtered through a sintered crucible, washed with aqueous alcohol (1 : 1) and finally with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over $CaCl_2$, yield 1.3 g. (Found : Ga, 34.1 ; I, 37.79 ; H_2O , 1.84. Calcd. for $Ga_5(IO_6)_3 \cdot H_2O$; Ga, 33.6 ; I, 36.81 ; H_2O , 1.73%). The reaction can be represented as :

Preparation of lithium gallium periodate, $Li_7Ga(IO_6)_3 \cdot 4H_2O$: Gallium sulphate (5 g) solution in water (20 ml) was added to KIO_4 (4.5 g) solution in KOH (3N). The mixture was stirred by a magnetic stirrer for 4 hr with slow heating. A colourless potassium gallium periodate solution was obtained which was filtered through a sintered crucible. Lithium sulphate (5 g) solution in water (15 ml) was then added to the filtrate. A white precipitate formed which was filtered through a sintered crucible, washed with aqueous alcohol (1 : 1) to free it from alkali, lithium periodate and other impurities and finally with ether. The compound was dried in a vacuum desiccator over $CaCl_2$, yield 2.1 g. (Found : Li, 7.94 ; Ga, 10.71 ; I, 39.89 ; H_2O ; 11.16. Calcd. for $Li_7Ga(IO_6)_3 \cdot 4H_2O$; Li, 7.59 ; Ga, 10.95 ; I, 39.93 ; H_2O , 11.32%).

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS

Compound	Weight of the compounds (g)	Weight of the residue (g)		Analysis of the residue			
		Found	Calcd.	%Ga		%Li	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
$Ga_5(IO_6)_3 \cdot H_2O$	0.0598	0.0274	0.0270	73.92	74.38	—	—
$Li_7Ga(IO_6)_3 \cdot 4H_2O$	0.0715	0.0225	0.0222	34.9	35.2	24.13	24.89

* Author for correspondence.

Analysis: Gallium was estimated⁸ as Ga_2O_3 , iodine was analysed following the method of Willard and Furman⁴. Lithium was estimated by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AA 6), water was determined by heating the sample at 120° for 1 hr.

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of the two compounds has been confirmed as $\text{Ga}_5(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by chemical analyses with the formula weights of 1035.5 and 636, respectively.

Oxidation numbers were determined by iodometry and Mohr salt titration⁸. In iodometric titration, a known aliquot was taken in a conical flask, 2 g solid KI (A.R.) was added and the liberated iodine titrated with standard thiosulphate solution in 0.2 N acid medium. It was found that 24 moles of thiosulphate were required per mole of $\text{Ga}_5(\text{IO}_6)_3$ but in the case of $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3$, 16 moles of this were required as per the following reactions:

In Mohr salt titration, an aliquot in 2 N H_2SO_4 was treated with excess Mohr solution and the resulting solution was titrated back with standard dichromate solution. It was found that 6 moles of Fe(II) solution were consumed by one mole of $\text{Ga}_5(\text{IO}_6)_3$ whereas 4 moles of Fe(II) were consumed for each mole of $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3$ as per the following reactions:

These results indicate that trivalent gallium and heptavalent iodine are present in both the compounds.

Magnetic moment measurements show that both the compounds are diamagnetic in nature at room temperature.

The ir spectra of the compounds are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 which were recorded in CsI phase from $4000-200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Strong and broad bands observed in the range $3520-2920 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for both the compounds can be accounted for the presence of OH mode of vibration. Broadening of the band is likely to arise from hydrogen bonding of the type $-\text{OH} \cdots \text{O}$. The peak at $1640-1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to stretching H_2O vibration, $\delta \text{ I}-\text{OH}$ was observed at $1380-1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for both the compounds. At lower wavelengths the spectra are very complicated, $\nu \text{ I}-\text{O}$ ranges⁸ from $750-630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. $\delta (\text{O}-\text{I}-\text{O})$ vibration occurs at $440-500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the grating vibrations at $280-310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The peak at 390 cm^{-1} present in the simple salt is absent in the complex. A peak at 610 cm^{-1} is also observed with the gallium complex. Metal oxygen band may also be present in the lower region^{7,9}. It is, however, difficult to assign the position in this region.

Diffused reflectance spectra (Figs. 3 and 4) of the compounds show no absorption band in the visible region but a band in the uv region at 210 nm due to presence of IO_6^{5-} species⁸ in both the compounds.

The stepwise thermal decomposition of the compounds has been shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Both the compounds lose weight at 110 to 140° for removal of water molecules. The decomposition of both the compounds continues with rise in temperature. The end product is the oxide of gallium for gallium periodate and the mixed oxides of lithium and gallium for lithium gallium periodate.

The potentiometric titration (Fig. 7) of $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with standard Na_2SO_3 solution shows a point of inflection at a potential of 0.34 volt vs SCE. The volume of Na_2SO_3 solution at this inflection point corresponds to 8 equivalents per mole of the complex. This indicates the standard potential

Fig. 1. Infrared spectra of $\text{Ga}_5(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 2. Infrared spectra of $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 3. Diffused reflectance spectrum of $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 4. Diffused reflectance spectra of $\text{Ga}_6(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

for $[\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2]^{7-}/\text{Ga}^{3+}, \text{I}^-$ system. The process of reduction may be represented by the equation :

The experimental result is in excellent agreement with the theoretical value (Table 2). The potential value also indicates that the species $\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2^{7-}$ is a strong oxidant.

The paper electrophoresis study of the mother liquor in KOH confirms that the compound

$[\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ contains the anionic species $[\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2]^{7-}$ giving the test of Ga^{3+} and IO_6^{5-} at the same zone of the paper, using 0.1 N KNO_3 solution as the carrier electrolyte.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION WITH STANDARD SODIUM SULPHITE SOLUTION

Weight of $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ taken	Vol. of sod. sulphite solution required (from the curve)	Strength of the sod. sulphite solution	Calcd. value of $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$
0.00505 g	1.975 ml	0.065 N	0.00510 g

Fig. 5. TG curve of $\text{Ga}_2(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 6. TG curve of $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Powder X-ray photograph of the compound $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is taken and interplanar spacings have also been calculated. Results are given in Table 3.

Infrared spectral studies furnish very good information on the presence of I-OH bonds. The structure of the compound $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may therefore be proposed as in Fig. 8 where both the gallium and iodine atoms are hexacoordinated and have octahedral geometry. There will be some

Fig. 7. Potentiometric titration of $\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3^-$ with standard sodium sulphite solution.

TABLE 3—POWDER X-RAY PHOTOGRAPH DATA OF THE COMPOUND $\text{Li}_7\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Intensity	d Value
s	4.90
vs	4.44
s	3.85
w	2.706
w	2.528
vw	2.429
s(b)	2.080
vw	1.895
w	1.6287
ms	1.475

Fig. 8

distortion from the idealised octahedral geometry due to different Ga-O and I-O bond lengths.

A complete structure can be revealed from X-ray crystallographic studies.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. N. K. Sengupta, Geological Survey of India, Calcutta for the estimation of lithium, Dr. (Mrs.) R. Guha, Geological Survey of India, Calcutta for recording powder X-ray photograph and Sri Kamal Krishna Mazumder, F. C. College, Diamond Harbour, for help and suggestions.

References

1. L. O. W. BAKER, L. LABIODA, J. GROCHOWSKI and H. G. MUKHERJEE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 102, 8274.

BAKER, MUKHERJEE & SARKAR : SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERISATION OF PERIODATE ETC.

2. A. A. VERDIZODE and M. M. MEKHTIEV, *Uch. Zap. Azerb. Gos. Univ. Ser. Nat. Mekh. Astron. Fiz. Khim.*, 1958, **13**, 183.
3. WILLARD and DIEHL, "Advanced Quantitative Analysis", D. Van Nostrand, N. Y., 2nd printing, p. 312.
4. H. H. WILLARD and N. H. FURMAN, "Elementary Quantitative Analysis", D. Van Nostrand, N. Y., 1940, p. 320.
5. H. G. MUKHERJEE and B. K. CHOUDHURY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1098.
- 6(a). H. SEIBERT, *Fortschr. Chem. Forsch.*, 1967, **8**, 470.
- (b). A. H. J. LOKIO and J. R. KYRKI, *Soumen Kemistilehti*, 1973, **B46**, 206.
7. F. PETRE, J. HRADILOVA and B. HAJEK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 1485.
8. C. E. CROUTHAMEL and D. S. MARTIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3031.